

A New Reagent System for the Determination of Captan (*N*-Trichloromethylthiotetrahydrophthalimide) Pesticide

MADHUSRI BHATTACHARJEE and V. K. GUPTA*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010

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Captan (*N*-trichloromethylthiotetrahydrophthalimide) is a general fungicide (TLV 5 mg m⁻³) for treatment of soil and seed borne diseases¹. It is non-phototoxic.

In the present communication, a modified Fujiwara reaction reported for polyhalogenated compounds² has been developed for the detection of captan. The method is based on the reaction of captan with pyridine and alkali on mild heating, forming an orange coloured chromophore. The colour is discharged by addition of acetic acid, followed by the addition of sulphanilic-formic acid reagent to obtain a yellow-orange coloured dye with a λ_{max} at 500 nm. This modification increases the stability and sensitivity of the Fujiwara reaction. Such modification has already been proposed for increasing the sensitivity of Fujiwara reaction^{3,4}. The method³ uses benzidine-formic acid reagent which is highly carcinogenic and so in the present method it has been replaced by sulphanilic-formic acid reagent.

Results and Discussion

One ml of pyridine and 1 ml or 5 M sodium hydroxide were required for maximum colour intensity. Excess of sodium hydroxide made the solution slightly cloudy due to undissolved sodium hydroxide. Two ml of acetic acid was sufficient for decolourisation of the orange colour; an excess amount, however, does not effect the reaction. A minimum of 2 ml of sulphanilic acid in 50% formic acid was required for maximum colour intensity during regeneration of colour. An excess

of sulphanilic-formic acid reagent decreased the colour intensity.

The yellow-orange coloured dye was found to be stable for ~15 min and thereafter showed gradual decrease in intensity. The dye showed maximum absorbance at 500 nm. The reagent blank showed no absorbance in this range. The maximum absorbance and stability of the dye formed was found in the pH range 4–6.

The colour system obeyed Beer's law in the range of 1–6 ppm of captan. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $4.2 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0071 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.003 and 2.08% respectively, for 1 ppm of captan.

Effect of various foreign species was studied by adding known amounts of foreign species to 1 ppm of captan prior to analysis and the tolerance limit (ppm) was found to be as follows : Ca^{II}, Cd^{II}, DDT, 1000; Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, 800; Pb^{II}, Be^{II}, 600; carbaryl, propoxur, 2,4-D, 2,4,5-T, Zn^{II}, Mg^{II}, nitrite, 500; Sn^{II}, Hg^{II}, 400; Fe^{III}, 250; malathion, parathion, paraquat, phosphate, 150; BHC, 100 (causing an error of $\pm 2\%$ in absorbance value). It was found that the method is free from the interference of most of the inorganic ions and other pesticides.

The method has been used for determining captan in fruits and grains. Since the samples analysed were found to be free from captan,

fruits like grapes, wheat and paddy grains were spiked with known amounts of captan. After 2–3 h, captan was extracted in acetone-methanol (1 : 1) solvent and determined by the proposed method. The recovery ranged from 90–96%.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer was used.

A stock solution of captan (Northern Minerals Limited) (1 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared in acetone-methanol mixture (1 : 1). A 1% sulphanilic acid was prepared in 50% formic acid. Glacial acetic acid, pyridine, 6 M HCl and 5 M aqueous NaOH solutions were used. All chemicals were of A.R. grade and captan was recrystallised (m.p. 178°).

Procedure :

To an aliquot containing 1–6 ppm captan, pyridine (1 ml) and 5 M NaOH (1 ml) were added. The contents were kept in water at 70° for 2 min and shaken occasionally. The orange coloured solution obtained was cooled in ice-cold water and then decolourised with glacial acetic

acid (2 ml). To this solution sulphanilic acid-formic acid reagent (2 ml) and 6 M HCl (1 ml) were added and allowed to stand for 5 min. The volume was made upto 10 ml with water and the orange-yellow coloured polymethine dye having an absorbance maxima at 500 nm was measured against a colourless reagent blank

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